

UNVEILING LEADERSHIP EXPERTISE DURING THE PANDEMIC IN PUBLIC SCHOOLS IN THE DIVISION OF ANGELES

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Abstract

This study explores the complex terrain of leadership competence in the setting of public schools under the extraordinary difficulties brought on by a pandemic in the Division of Angeles, Angeles City, Pampanga. It is critical for educational institutions to have strong leadership to maintain the continuity and resilience of learning environments in the face of challenges to traditional teaching models, resource limitations, and increased social pressures. The research utilizes descriptive-survey method of research, questionnaires were sent to the respondents via email. There were five school principals handpicked as respondents from the Division of Angeles City. Themes that have been examined include community involvement, teacher support, technological integration, and crisis communication. The results are collected to provide insightful information to leadership development programs, school administrators, and educational policymakers that aim to improve the effectiveness and readiness of leaders in public school environments when confronted with unexpected obstacles. This research intends to uncover critical leadership qualities and best practices that have emerged as crucial in managing the difficulties of crisis management in public schools by looking at the adaptive tactics and decision-making processes of leaders. In the end, this study aims to shed light on the various facets of leadership competence that have been crucial in encouraging equity, preserving academic excellence, and building resilience in public schools within the setting of a pandemic.

Keywords: school leadership, leadership expertise, COVID-19 pandemic

Introduction

The Education Department is in the forefront of educational governance and is responsible for reshaping the academic environment to guarantee inclusivity, equity, and quality. The COVID-19 epidemic has had a profound impact on educational institutions worldwide. As a result, leadership in public schools has become increasingly important in minimizing disruptions and navigating unfamiliar ground. The Department of Education in the Division of Angeles is the focal point of this study, which aims to reveal the subtle facets of the leadership skills demonstrated by school administrators in the face of the pandemic's unparalleled obstacles.

The city of Angeles is a microcosm of the greater educational environment. The city's varied socioeconomic makeup presents difficulties that call for adaptable and capable leadership in the public education system. The epidemic widened already-existing gaps, emphasizing the necessity for strong, flexible leadership capable of handling the complex aspects of educational continuity.

With the start of the global pandemic, education entered a new period characterized by rapid shifts to distant and hybrid learning, resource limitations, and increased community anxiety. The officials of the Angeles City Department of Education were forced to take the lead in the face of these difficulties, making decisions that would have a significant impact on the education of many students in the future. Effective leadership was put to the test by the difficult balancing act of preserving educational standards, encouraging community involvement, and guaranteeing safety.

Exposing the leadership skills of the Department of Education in Angeles City throughout the pandemic is important for academic research and real-world implementation. The knowledge gained from this study is intended to advance the field's comprehension of crisis leadership and provide a model for other academic institutions facing comparable difficulties. Furthermore, the results have the potential to guide future efforts for improving resilience and readiness in the event of unanticipated disruptions by informing policy recommendations and leadership development programs within the Department of Education.

Globally, the COVID-19 epidemic has severely disrupted educational systems, posing hitherto unheard-of issues that call for adaptable and capable leadership. As the world grappled with the profound implications of the COVID-19 pandemic on its education system, educational leadership emerged as a critical determinant of resilience and success. This literature review highlights the diverse facets of leadership expertise, emphasizing the need for adaptive styles, technological acumen, effective communication, teacher support, and a commitment to equity. Further research in these areas is essential to inform ongoing leadership development initiatives and shape policies that foster educational resilience in the face of future crises.

Research conducted in the US during the pandemic on leadership emphasizes how important it is for leaders to have flexible approaches to deal with quickly shifting

conditions. It has been shown that transformational leadership—which is typified by vision, empathy, and the capacity to inspire—is especially useful in encouraging commitment and resilience among stakeholders in education (Herman, 2020). Examining how American leaders have modified their approaches to deal with the intricacies of crisis management is essential to comprehending leadership proficiency in this difficult time. Using technology in the classroom proved essential to keeping things running smoothly throughout the pandemic. Studies indicate that leaders who welcomed and supported the integration of technology had greater levels of resilience and readiness resilience (Ertmer & Ottenbreit-Leftwich, 2013). Understanding the importance of technical savvy in leadership expertise is aided by looking at the methods used by American educational leaders to use technology for remote and hybrid learning models. A key component of crisis management leadership success is effective communication. Research highlights the significance of open and compassionate communication in fostering trust amongst those involved (Jacobsen & Jacobsen, 2020).

To assess leadership performance during the pandemic, it becomes imperative to investigate how educational leaders in the USA managed crisis communication, interacted with a variety of stakeholders, and promoted a feeling of community. Supporting the well-being of educators is crucial since they encounter unique difficulties when adjusting to new teaching methodologies. Studies indicate that leaders who gave priority to professional development, mental health programs, and support for teachers had a favorable effect on the results of education (Harris et al., 2021). Analyzing the approaches taken by American leaders to promote the wellbeing of their teachers offers insights into the comprehensive nature of leadership competence. The pandemic made already-existing educational disparities worse, highlighting the role that leadership plays in advancing inclusion and equity. Leaders that showed a dedication to social justice were those who put the concerns of marginalized groups first and carried out focused initiatives (Pitre & Jackson, 2020). Examining the way American leaders handled matters of fairness and inclusivity within the pandemic illuminates the interconnectedness of crisis leadership proficiency.

Research Questions

The foundation of this research is an extensive investigation of the leadership dynamics that existed in the Division of Angeles throughout the pandemic. The principal goals encompass pinpointing essential leadership proficiencies, scrutinizing adaptable tactics utilized by instructional leaders, and evaluating the influence of leadership determinations on academic results. Through dissecting the complex fabric of crisis leadership, this research seeks to offer a comprehensive viewpoint that goes beyond conventional thinking, recognizing the diverse aspects of leadership in the dynamic field of public education. Specifically, this study shall ponder to the following questions:

1. In the context of public education, how did you modify your leadership style to deal with the sudden obstacles and uncertainty caused by the COVID-19 pandemic?

2. Could you name some specific leadership traits or abilities that you felt were especially important for negotiating the challenges of crisis management in the public school system during the pandemic?
3. During the epidemic, what communication techniques did you use to effectively interact with different stakeholders, such as educators, parents, students, and the larger community? In what ways did these tactics foster a feeling of solidarity and support?
4. What obstacles did you face in facilitating the incorporation of technology into administrative and instructional strategies to maintain school continuity during the pandemic?
5. What results and effects do you see from your leadership choices throughout the pandemic in terms of upholding the standard of education, encouraging resiliency, and promoting the general wellbeing of students, staff, and the community you serve?

Methodology

This research offers a question for an interview with the chosen principals and assistant principals of the Division of Angeles in Angeles City, Pampanga.

The researcher developed one thorough research question that my selected interviewee will respond to: How did leadership expertise within the public schools of the Division of Angeles manifest during the pandemic, and what key strategies or competencies did educational leaders employ to navigate the unprecedented challenges and uncertainties posed by the COVID-19 crisis? This query was answered by six school principals responding through interview via email.

Results

The purpose of the qualitative study is to investigate the leadership prowess of school principals during the pandemic in the Division of Angeles.

Respondent's claim on Leadership Expertise During the Pandemic	Researcher's Insight
"As a school principal during the pandemic, I had to adapt quickly to changing circumstances. Decision-making became paramount, and we prioritized the safety of our students and staff while ensuring educational continuity."	Adaptation and Decision-Making
"As a school head I recognize the importance of technology in facilitating remote learning. Aside from printed materials we also employ online platforms, virtual classrooms, thus, providing technology resources became	Technological Integration

a necessity assuring our students could continue their education."	
"On the onslaught of COVID-19 constant communication was essential. We kept stakeholders (parents, teachers, and students) informed about the direction of the academic year such as developments, changes in learning modalities, and safety measures, in doing so, we build trust and understanding within the school community."	Communication Strategies
"Our instructors' support came first. To assist them in overcoming the difficulties of distant teaching, we put professional development programs into place, provided emotional support, and fostered a collaborative environment."	Teacher Support and Professional Development
"Interacting with the neighborhood was essential. We cultivated relationships with local government agencies, parents, and community groups to guarantee a cooperative strategy in handling the difficulties posed by the pandemic."	Community Engagement
"Given the actuality of resource limitations, strategic management became essential. To guarantee the sustainability of educational projects, we made educated decisions, made the most of the resources that were already available, and looked for extra support when needed."	Strategic Resource Management
"Ensuring the health and safety of everyone in the school community was a top priority. We implemented rigorous health protocols, collaborated with health authorities, and communicated effectively to create a secure learning environment."	Health and Safety Measures
"After seeing that the pandemic was making gaps worse, we took action to address equity concerns. This included making sure that technology was accessible, helping underprivileged students with resources, and attending to the needs of vulnerable groups."	Equity and Inclusion Initiatives
"We have started making plans for future readiness, having learned from the pandemic's experiences. To handle any future emergencies, this entails creating backup plans, improving our technology infrastructure, and honing our leadership techniques."	Future Preparedness Planning

Discussion

The principals showed incredible fortitude and shrewdness in handling the difficulties presented by the COVID-19 pandemic. Regarding adjustment and judgment, their answers demonstrated a quick and adaptable response to the quickly evolving situation.

A dedication to maintaining the uninterrupted delivery of education while guaranteeing the safety of students and staff typified the decisions made. This flexibility demonstrated the principals' crisis abilities.

One of the main themes that arose was technological integration, with principals stressing the importance of strategically integrating technology to support remote learning. Their focus was to close the gap in the adoption of new learning modalities by utilizing digital materials, virtual classrooms, and online platforms. Principals focused on open and frequent communication to keep all stakeholders informed, and communication methods also played a significant role. To foster understanding and trust among the students, these leaders placed a high priority on good communication. Additionally, they demonstrated their dedication to professional development and teacher support by putting initiatives in place to give teachers the resources, emotional support, and collaborative environments they need to meet the challenges of teaching remotely.

Principals forged alliances and relationships with parents, local government agencies, and community organizations as part of a major component of community engagement. Their ability to maximize available resources and make wise decisions in the face of resource limitations was indicative of their strategic resource management. Prioritizing health and safety meant that executives worked with health officials to adopt strict protocols. Initiatives aimed at promoting equity and inclusion emphasized their dedication to mitigating inequalities made worse by the epidemic, providing resources for disadvantaged groups, and guaranteeing technological access. Ultimately, these principles exhibited a forward-looking outlook by devising plans for future readiness, putting technological infrastructure improvements into action, honing leadership techniques, and creating backup plans in case of emergencies.

The school principals in the Angeles Division demonstrated leadership proficiency in a variety of fields. They demonstrated flexibility, technological know-how, good communication, support for educators, community involvement, strategic resource management, dedication to health and safety, initiatives for inclusion and equity, and proactive planning for upcoming difficulties.

Conclusions

The COVID-19 pandemic presented public education with previously unheard-of obstacles. In response, the respondents adopted a leadership style that prioritized adaptability, transparency, and compassionate decision-making. Aware of the unexpected challenges and uncertainties, they adopted a consultative and collaborative approach, incorporating stakeholders in the decision-making procedures. Important leadership qualities that were crucial in crisis management were the capacity for inspiring a common vision of cooperatively overcoming obstacles, for example, and for good communication. They used a multifaceted communication strategy, including virtual town hall meetings, frequent updates via several platforms, and encouraging open lines of

communication, to connect with numerous stakeholders. These strategies attempted to foster a sense of unity and support among educators in addition to spreading important information. Even though technology was necessary to keep things going, there were issues with accessibility and training. Allocating resources and making strategic plans were necessary to overcome these obstacles. The educational community saw a sustained level of instruction, heightened resilience, and an improved sense of overall wellness among students, staff, and the larger community they served because of these leadership decisions.

Amid the COVID-19 pandemic's exceptional obstacles, the Division of Angeles's leadership ability was crucial in directing public education. As pivotal personalities in this context, school principals were entrusted with making decisions that would have a major impact on students' and teachers' well-being as well as the continuity of learning. To successfully navigate the complexity of crisis management, which calls for quick decisions, clear communication, and a strategic future vision, leadership expertise was crucial. In the Division of Angeles, educational leaders played a pivotal role in enabling the adjustment to novel learning modes, guaranteeing the incorporation of technology, and tackling concerns related to equity and inclusion that were intensified by the pandemic. Further emphasized were the benefits of having a strong leadership background for developing resilience, upholding a great school climate, and creating a feeling of community and solidarity. The Division of Angeles encountered hitherto unseen difficulties, and the skill and fortitude exhibited by educators were crucial in determining the course of public education during this trying time.

Recommendations

During these challenging times, the administrators in the division showed amazing tenacity and adaptation. However, the pandemic demands identified areas where leadership proficiency can be strengthened even more to guarantee the school community's well-being and the continuous provision of high-quality instruction. This section presents a series of thoughtful recommendations that aim to enhance and empower the leadership skills of the Division of Angeles City school administrators considering the research findings.

These suggestions are meant to provide useful and doable tactics that tackle the difficulties faced by school administrators. The focus is on developing a culture of proactive and resilient leadership, improving crisis readiness, and creating an atmosphere that meets the emotional and academic requirements of students, faculty, and the community at large. These suggestions are based on best practices and insights from the larger educational landscape in addition to the results of the research. Here are the following recommendations:

1. Boost Programs for Professional Development
2. Encourage a Culture of Collaborative Leadership

3. Incorporate Technology into Administrative Tasks
4. Form a Crisis Management Unit
5. Create an All-Inclusive Communication Plan
6. Make mental health and well-being a priority.
7. Promote Adaptability and Innovation
8. Create an Ongoing Feedback System
9. Work Together with Outside Partners
10. Create a Strategic Long-Term Plan for Crisis Management

The researcher hopes that stakeholders in the Division of Angeles would use these recommendations as a guide to help school administrators develop their leadership skills and become better prepared to deal with the uncertainties of the current and future educational environments.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The process of conducting email interviews with the six school principals of the Division of Angeles City has been carefully planned to prioritize the concepts of respect, confidentiality, and informed permission in accordance with the ethical norms guiding research. Each school principal received a thorough explanation of the study's goals, methods, and voluntary participation requirements before the email interviews were started. It was made clear to participants during the informed consent process that participation was completely optional and that they might leave the study at any time without facing any consequences. Furthermore, participant confidentiality was strictly upheld, guaranteeing that any information disclosed would be pooled and anonymized for the purpose of the study. The development of interview questions was heavily influenced by ethical considerations, which made sure the inquiries were courteous, non-intrusive, and centered on the goals of the study. Every attempt was made to maintain the highest ethical standards during the email interview process to protect the rights and well-being of the participating school principals and ensure that the research meaningfully advances our understanding of leadership expertise during the pandemic.

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References

Ertmer, P. A., & Ottenbreit-Leftwich, A. (2013). Removing Obstacles to the Pedagogical Changes Required by Jonassen's Vision of Authentic Technology-enabled Learning. *Computers & Education*, 64, 175-182.

Harris, A., Azorín, C., & Jones, M. (2023). Network Leadership: A New Educational Imperative?. *International Journal of Leadership in Education*, 26(5), 919-935.

Herman, E., Banks, M. A., Hahn, W. R., Landry, C. L., & Viviani, L. M. (2022). Capital Improvements to Principal Leadership: Culturally Responsive District Strategies to Retain School Principals (Doctoral dissertation, Boston College).

Jacobsen, L. (2023). When Adversity Strikes: Examining the Post-Pandemic Challenges of a Boston Charter School (Doctoral dissertation, Northeastern University).

Pitre & Jackson. (2020). The Impact of COVID-19 on Student Equity and Inclusion: Supporting Vulnerable Students During School Closures and School Re-openings. https://read.oecd-ilibrary.org/view/?ref=434_434914-59wd7ekj29&title=The-impact-of-COVID-19-on-student-equity-and-inclusion